

Phaeophyscia pusilloides

Pompom Shadow

: On the bark of deciduous trees.

: Small, grey, foliose thallus. Relatively common, defining feature are its powdery lobe tips, often with a pompom or distinct ball of soredia.

Lichens are the cooperative partnership between a fungus and many partners, including at least one or more algae and/or cyanobacteria. The body of a lichen is made of fungus that positions the partner in a thin layer near the surface where it is exposed to sunlight. The partner photosynthesizes and provides the fungus with nutrients. Most species in this pamphlet are foliose (meaning they have a leafy appearance and a bottom layer) because they are the easiest to see without magnification. There are many more species that are harder to spot! Try looking through a magnifying glass to see what else you can find!

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Cross section of a lichen:
A) upper cortex, B) algal layer,
C) medulla, D) lower cortex,
E) rhizines

Pertusaria pustulata

Warty Warts

: On the bark of deciduous trees.

: Thin, smooth, shiny crustose thallus. Light grey to grey green. Apothecia wart-like, raised and bumpy with discs appearing as brown pores. Relatively small.

Lichens are all around you. They can grow on all sorts of surfaces (called substrates) such as: rock, concrete, bark, bare ground, metal, and more. Lichens do not harm the plants they grow on but they can wear away stone very slowly.

Symbols used here:

: Where you'll find it

: Appearance and key features

Common Lichens Around Town

Seven common tree lichens in Mid-Atlantic and Northeast cities and towns

By Eli Denzer

Candelaria concolor
Candleflame

: One of the most common species on street trees.

: Bright yellow to pale greenish yellow. Very small lobes with finely divided tips that dissolve into granular soredia. Usually found growing together in large patches.

Physcia millegrana
Spangled Rosette

: One of the most common species in urban areas, on bark.

: Small, white to grey thallus, narrow lobes with edges that dissolve into powdery grains. Individuals often grow together into large patches.

Flavoparmelia caperata
Common Greenshield

: On bark, frequent.

: Large, foliose, yellow-green. Lobes broad, smooth tips, wrinkled towards center. Lower surface black with brown edges. Soredia produced on lobes in and around center.

Phaeophyscia rubropulchra
Orange-cored Shadow

: On the bark of deciduous trees.

: Small, upper surface brownish-green or brownish grey; **medulla orange-red**; often grows in large patches of many individuals.

TIP!: The red medulla is the best clue to find this species. Gently scrape your nail on the top to reveal the bright middle layer.

Physcia stellaris
Starry Rosette

: Found on bark and wood. Benches, fences, twigs, and trunks, frequent.

: Small, light grey, foliose; apothecia gray to black (upper left), common; pycnidia black (lower left), on lobes.

Lecanora strobilina
Yellow Mealy Rims

: On the bark of deciduous trees and conifers. Commonly found on pine cone scales.

: Crustose, light green, edge of thallus indistinct. Apothecia common, round, 0.5-1.0 mm in diameter, white powdery or mealy rim contrasting with disc, disc light yellow/yellow green.

